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"THROUGH SLEEPLESS NIGHTS"

The sun has set, the moon will rise,
They rest in peace, yet I strive for prize.
The night unfolds with zephyr's breeze,
Time may run, but steadfast hearts are keys.

A thousand scars and countless falls, yet my faith still blooms,
Dreams bound to my soul will fill the room.
Others sleep gently, yet my light stays on,
I've yawned a thousand times, yet ponder till dawn.

Dreams are not far, yet not so near,
Unbelieving impossible, yet hoping sincere.
Breaking points are swift, yet progress slow,
To dream is easy, but fulfillment is woe.

Beneath exhaustion lies endless aspiration,
Within each murmur of failure, rigid vision.
As despair creeps closer, so does my mission,
For beneath each struggle burns firm devotion.

Through sleepless nights and ceaseless progression,
Comes daily doubt and deep confusion.
Yet hunger fuels my soul's salvation,
For from starvation, blooms ambition.

